

**FUNDAMENTALS OF CORRECTIONAL PEDAGOGY AND INCLUSIVE
EDUCATIONAL PROCESSES**

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15287401>

Abstract. *This study presents information on the basic principles of correctional pedagogy and the history of its origin, as well as new modern methods of using interactive methods based on pedagogical technologies. Based on this information, it is possible to further improve the quality of education through the use of new pedagogical teaching technologies in inclusive education. During this study, teachers are given instructions on creating new methods based on innovative pedagogical approaches to inclusive education.*

Keywords: *Correctional pedagogy, inclusive education, interactive methods, pedagogical teaching technology, interactive education.*

**ОСНОВЫ КОРРЕКЦИОННОЙ ПЕДАГОГИКИ И ИНКЛЮЗИВНЫХ
ОБРАЗОВАТЕЛЬНЫХ ПРОЦЕССОВ**

Аннотация. *В исследовании представлена информация об основных принципах коррекционной педагогики и истории ее зарождения, а также о новых современных методах использования интерактивных методов на основе педагогических технологий обучения. На основе этой информации станет возможным дальнейшее повышение качества образования за счет использования новых педагогических технологий обучения в инклюзивном образовании. Это исследование предоставит учителям рекомендации по созданию новых методов, основанных на инновационных педагогических подходах к инклюзивному образованию.*

Ключевые слова: *Коррекционная педагогика, инклюзивное образование, интерактивные методы, педагогические технологии обучения, интерактивное образование.*

KORREKSION PEDAGOGIKA ASOSLARI VA INKLYUZIV TA'LIM JARAYONLARI

Annotatsiya. Ushbu tadqiqotda korreksion pedagogikaning asosiy tamoyillari va korreksion pedagogikaning kelib chiqish tarixi, shuningdek pedagogic o'itish texnologiyalarga asoslangan holda interfaol metodlarni qo'llashning yangi zamonaviy usullari haqida ma'lumotlar keltirib o'tilgan. Ushbu ma'lumotlarga asoslangan holda inklyuziv ta'limda yangi pedagogik o'qitish texnologiyalaridan foydalanish orqali ta'lim sifatini yanada oshirish mumkin bo'ladi. Ushbu tadqiqot davomida inklyuziv ta'limga innovatsion pedagogik yondashuvlar asosida yangi metodlarni yaratish bo'yicha o'qituvchilarga ko'rsatmalar berib boriladi.

Kalit so'zlar: Korreksion pedagogika, inklyuziv ta'lim, interfaol metodlar, pedagogik o'qitish texnologiyasi, interfaol ta'lim.

Introduction

The main goal of correctional pedagogy is to study the necessary conditions for the education of anomalous children and to provide educators and teachers with methods for correcting, eliminating or making their shortcomings as invisible as possible. The task of correctional pedagogy is to organize integrated, inclusive or differential education, studying the causes and types of anomalies, and the features of the psychophysiological development of anomalous children, and to engage in their education and upbringing. Correctional pedagogy is considered a new science compared to other sciences. This science began to develop mainly in the middle of the 19th century.

The great psychologist Professor L.S. Vygotsky made a great contribution to the development of this science. In 1925, the Institute of Experimental Defectology was founded in Moscow. This institute was headed by L.S. Vygotsky. L.S. Vygotsky studied the features of the development of anomalous children and also developed a doctrine about the complex structure of defects. In the book "The Main Problems of Correctional Pedagogy", he studied the need for developmental education with anomalous children, studied the methods of correction and compensation, and highlighted the methods of their implementation. The main tasks of correctional pedagogy. There are general laws for the development, education and upbringing of anomalous children of various categories. The basis of correctional pedagogy is a comprehensive, physiological and psychological study of anomalous children, the tasks of which include:

- correction of defects and identification of correctional and compensatory possibilities of a child with various developmental deficiencies;
- solving the problems of anomalous children in order to implement differentiated education and upbringing;
- identification and registration of anomalous children;

- scientific development of methods for early diagnosis of developmental anomalies;
- development of measures to correct, eliminate or reduce developmental defects in children;
- development of a system of preventive measures to prevent abnormal childhood.

Interactive education, interactive methods are a system of methods based on regular communication, a system of education and methods with the cooperation and active participation of students. In other words, interactive methods of teaching are a special form of organizing cognitive and communicative activities, in which students are involved in the process of cognition, they have the opportunity to understand and think about what they know and think. The role of the teacher in interactive lessons is partly to direct the activities of students to achieve the goals of the lesson. The peculiarity of these methods is that they are implemented only through the joint work of the teacher and students. Currently, modern teaching methods are widely used in the educational process. The use of modern teaching methods leads to high efficiency in the teaching process. It is advisable to choose these methods based on the didactic task of each lesson. Enriching the traditional lesson form with various methods that activate the activities of students leads to an increase in the level of students' mastery. Today, in a number of developed countries, methods that form the basis of extensive experience in the use of modern pedagogical technologies that guarantee the effectiveness of the educational process are being developed under the name of interactive methods. Interactive teaching methods are currently the most widespread and widely used in all types of educational institutions. At the same time, there are many types of interactive teaching methods, and there are currently suitable ones for the implementation of almost all tasks of the educational process. In practice, it is possible to select the appropriate ones for specific purposes and apply them accordingly. This situation has now created the problem of choosing the right interactive teaching methods to achieve specific goals. This requires rational organization of the lesson process, constant stimulation of the interest of the learners by the teacher, their activity in the learning process, division of the educational material into small parts, use of methods such as brainstorming, work in small groups, discussion, problem situations, reference texts, projects, role-playing games to reveal their content, and encouragement of learners to independently perform practical exercises.

Interactive teaching methods are often used in conjunction with various forms of training technologies. The use of these methods increases the activity of the participants in the training and improves the effectiveness of training. The choice of methods and methodological approaches by a teacher in preparation for a new topic means balancing their interchangeability in terms of time and didactic purpose. As a result, conditions are created to ensure a high level of intellectual and practical activity of children with disabilities.

Properly applied methods deepen knowledge of objective reality and increase the holistic and scientific-theoretical level of training. Consistently selected teaching methods lead to a certain level of development of knowledge and professional interest, activation of independent practical activity. In pedagogy, a large number of criteria for choosing traditional methods have been developed, more than twenty of them have been cited in the works of didactic scientists in recent years. One of the most serious didactic problems is the question of what the choice of teaching methods depends on. The criterion for choosing interactive methods is their high orientation towards solving problems of developing education and upbringing. This criterion is introduced by assessing the possibilities of solving tasks in one or another sphere of different methods, since their possibilities in mastering elements of social experience are different. The next criterion for choosing interactive methods is their correspondence to the nature of the educational content. The content of the method is also determined as a part of the movement. Therefore, it is obvious that this criterion should be taken into account. If one method fully reveals the content of the subject, then another allows for its positive mastery. Another criterion for choosing interactive methods is their full compliance with the learning opportunities of children with disabilities, that is, ensuring the unity of internal and external conditions for effective learning activity.

Conclusion

Thus, the educational process in inclusive educational institutions is carried out within the framework of a multifaceted integrated system organized in accordance with modern forms and methods of teaching. In this case, each form performs its assigned tasks, but the set of forms and methods forms a single didactic complex. The implementation of this didactic complex is determined by the psychological and pedagogical laws of the educational process. One of the important requirements for the organization of modern education is to achieve high results in a short time without spending excessive mental and physical effort. Delivering certain theoretical knowledge to students in a short time, forming skills and competencies in them for a specific activity, as well as monitoring the activities of students, assessing the level of knowledge, skills and competencies acquired by them, requires the teacher to have high pedagogical skills and a new approach to the educational process.

References

1. Turemuratova, Aziza, Rita Kurbanova, and Barno Saidboyeva. "EDUCATIONAL TRADITIONS IN SHAPING THE WORLDVIEW OF YOUNG PEOPLE IN FOLK PEDAGOGY." *Modern Science and Research* 2.10 (2023): 318-322.

2. Kurbanova, R. J., and B. E. Saidboeva. "MAKTAB VA OILADA ESTETIK TARBIYANI SHAKLLANTIRISH JARAYONIDA O'QUVCHILARNING AKSIOLOGIK DUNYOQARASHINI RIVOJLANTIRISH." *Inter education & global study* 9 (2024): 114-121.
3. Jarasovna, Kurbanova Rita. "The Role of National Values in Shaping the Aesthetic Worldview of Schoolchildren." *International Journal of Pedagogics* 5.03 (2025): 55-58.
4. Asamatdinova, J., and B. Saidboeva. "Diagnosis and Correction of the Development of Value Orientation in Students in the Process of Moral and Aesthetic Education." *JournalNX* 9.6 (2023): 274-277.
5. Turemuratova, Aziza, and Kamola Yoldasheva. "PSYCHOLOGICAL CONFIDENTIALITY OF THE FORMATION OF STUDENTS'COLLABORATIVE SKILLS BASED ON MULTI-VECTOR APPROACHES IN EDUCATION." *Modern Science and Research* 4.4 (2025): 262-269.
6. Turemuratova, Aziza, Shahlo Matmuratova, and Nargisa Tajieva. "THE DEPENDENCE OF MULTI-VECTOR APPROACHES ON PEDAGOGICAL METHODS AND PSYCHOLOGICAL TRAINING IN IMPROVING STUDENTS'COLLABORATIVE SKILLS BASED ON THE EDUCATIONAL PROGRAM." *Modern Science and Research* 4.4 (2025): 50-55.
7. Turemuratova, Aziza, and Marhabo Kenjayeva. "KO'P VEKTORLI YONDASHUVLAR ASOSIDA TALABALARNING KOLLOBORATIV KO'NIKMALARINI RIVOJLANTIRISHNING PSIXOLOGIK TRENING USLUBI." *Modern Science and Research* 4.4 (2025): 252-261.
8. Turemuratova, Aziza, Umida Uzakbaeva, and Dilafro'z Nuriyeva. "BASIC CONCEPTS OF FAMILY PSYCHOLOGY AND OVERCOMING PSYCHOLOGICAL PROBLEMS." *Modern Science and Research* 4.4 (2025): 104-109.
9. Turemuratova, Aziza, Maftuna Masharipova, and Ma'mura Atabayeva. "RESEARCH ON IMPROVING STUDENTS'COLLABORATIVE SKILLS BASED ON MULTI-VECTOR PSYCHOLOGICAL TRAINING APPROACHES." *Modern Science and Research* 4.4 (2025): 90-97.
10. Begibaevna, Turemuratova Aziza, Kushbaeva Indira Tursinbaevna, and Dawletmuratova Raxila Genjemuratovna. "THE MAIN ESSENCE OF DEVELOPING STUDENTS'COLLABORATIVE SKILLS BASED ON MULTI-VECTOR

- PEDAGOGICAL APPROACHES IN MODERN EDUCATION." CURRENT RESEARCH JOURNAL OF PEDAGOGICS 5.09 (2024): 43-46.
11. Jarilkapovich, Matjanov Aman. "Program Technology for Choosing an Effective Educational Methodology Based on Modern Pedagogical Research in The Educational System." CURRENT RESEARCH JOURNAL OF PEDAGOGICS 6.02 (2025): 30-33.
 12. Jarilkapovich, Matjanov Aman. "USE OF PEDAGOGICAL METHODS BASED ON THE MODERN EDUCATIONAL PROGRAM TO INCREASE THE EFFECTIVENESS OF EDUCATION." European International Journal of Pedagogics 4.06 (2024): 26-33.
 13. Daribaev, Atabay, and Nazrgiza Sagindikova. "HISTORY OF PSYCHOLOGY." Modern Science and Research 3.1 (2024): 1162-1166.
 14. Turdimuratova, S. B., and N. J. Sagindikova. "PSIXOLOGIK DIAGNOSTIKA." Modern Science and Research 3.7 (2024).
 15. Polatovna, Rametullaeva Nadira, and OLIY TA'LIMDA INNOVATSION YONDASHUVLAR ASOSIDA. "PEDAGOGIK VA PSIXOLOGIK METODLARNI TAHLIL QILISHGA ASOSLANGAN TADQIQOTLAR." TA'LIM VA RIVOJLANISH TAHLILI ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI 3.12 (2023): 67-70.